

The Impact of Social Media Communication on Brand Association and Repurchase Intention in Local Beauty Brand in Indonesia

Elsamita Yolanda¹, Prof. Indrawati²

^{1,2}Economic and Business, Telkom University, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: People's demeanor and interactions in Indonesia have progressed into more digital, thus businesses and companies have shifted their marketing efforts to digital marketing. The objective of this investigation is to determine the effects of SMC on brand association and repurchase intention for a beauty brand in Indonesia, given the significant changes in people's behavior and interaction caused by the use of digital technology, particularly social media, as well as the rapid growth of the beauty industry in Indonesia. 290 samples were gathered utilizing an online survey form. Purposive sampling was employed to ensure respondent validity, and the results were assessed using SmartPLS 3.0's structural equation modeling (SEM) approach. This study discovered that social media communication had a positive and substantial effect on repurchase intention through brand association, with company-generated content having a stronger influence on repurchase intention than user-generated content.

KEYWORDS: brand association, firm-generated content, repurchase intention, social media communication, user-generated content.

INTRODUCTION

Since the COVID-19 epidemic in 2020, individual behavior and interactions have become entirely digital (Yusuf, 2021). This is consistent with the annual increase in internet and social media users (Palit et al., 2021; Riyanto, 2024). The majority of internet users utilize social media to communicate and entertain one another (Agusiady et al., 2024; Kanchan & Gaidhane, 2023). Indonesia is a significant player in the development of Southeast Asia's Internet and social media usage, and it will continue to rise (Herdiyani et al., 2022; Wono et al., 2023). Companies or brands are moving their marketing focus to digital, investing extensively in digital interaction transformation (Kemp, 2023; Kulikovskaja et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2023).

The FMGC industry dominates Indonesia's Top Brands in 2023 (Katadata, 2023). The care and beauty category is the best-selling and most popular category in 2023, contributing considerably to Indonesia's economic growth and propelling the sector forward (Annur, 2024; Limanseto, 2024; Lintin, 2023; Portal Informasi Indonesia, 2023). Wardah is the most popular and used local beauty brand in Indonesia in 2023, and it ranks first in the care and beauty category on the Top 50 Local Brands 2023 list (Katadata, 2023; Nurhayati, 2023). Wardah does marketing both offline by opening outlets in shopping malls and online by using social media and ecommerce platforms to uncover various opportunities to listen and engage customers (Tardin et al., 2020; Wardah Cosmetics, 2024). Social media communication (SMC) is a method for a company or brand to communicate with its target consumers by employing engaging social media content to improve consumer-brand interaction (Bu et al., 2020; Du Plessis, 2017; Wei et al., 2023). Social media marketing can enhance a brand's value in consumers' minds and hearts, increase consumer interaction and engagement, feelings toward a brand, eWOM, and willingness to pay premium prices (Algharabat et al., 2020; Bu et al., 2020; Huerta-Álvarez et al., 2020; Müller & Christandl, 2019; Torres et al., 2018). SMC includes two forms of content: firm-generated content (FGC) and user-generated content (UGC) (Müller & Christandl, 2019). FGC examples include company-created articles or blogs, as well as content on official social media platforms. Meanwhile, consumer-generated content (UGC) includes social media posts, product reviews, comments, and testimonials (Cheung et al., 2020). According to some literature and previous research, UGC is more important than FGC because UGC can be trusted by target consumers, whereas FGC content can be controlled and manipulated by companies (Perera et al., 2023; Poulis et al., 2019; Schivinski et al., 2022; Zia et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, some other studies conclude that FGC is more essential than UGC due to the presence of fake news, and that consumers should exercise caution when acquiring product information from the Internet and social media (Cheung et al., 2020; Tardin et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2023). Knowing which material has the greatest influence on customers allows brands to focus their efforts on digital marketing that increases brand equity, allowing them to gain market share and increase sales.

According to literature studies, no research has been conducted to evaluate the characteristics of SMC on the object of beauty brands, particularly local beauty brands in Indonesia. The majority of past study has been focused on the electronic product sector, government, fast food restaurants, higher education institutions, fashion industry, and shopping centers (Cheung et al., 2020; Perera et al., 2023; Schivinski et al., 2022; Tardin et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2023; Zia et al., 2022). Thus, the goal of this study was to examine what types of material can influence repurchase intentions in the Wardah brand via consumer-based brand equity. Given that Wardah is the most popular beauty brand in 2023. In addition, Wardah also received seven awards in 2023 from LPPOM MUI Halal Award 2023, IHYA 2023 and London Fashion Week 2023 (KumparanWoman, 2022; Ludiyanto, 2023; Nur, 2023).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Media Communications (SMC)

Lin et al. (2023) define social media communication (SMC) as the creation and sharing of material based on relationships with other social media users. According to Koay et al. (2021), SMC is the The method by which firms connect and provide marketing offers online using social media tools to establish and maintain stakeholder relationships that can offer value by facilitating interaction, sharing information, recommending purchases, and being personalized based on consumer preferences. SMC is the use of social networks for advertising, user product evaluations, blogging, support, entertainment, and user and corporate marketing to promote brand loyalty through social media interactions (Zia et al., 2022).

Dimension of SMC

Firm-generated content (FGC) refers to any sort of content created by businesses to directly promote their brand on their official social media accounts (Perera et al., 2023). FGC consists of marketers or businesses who create online content with the goal of acquiring customers. The content can take the shape of Facebook postings, tweets, or YouTube videos uploaded by the company (Lin et al., 2023). FGC wants to raise brand awareness by discussing products and services. FGC is classified as different marketing communications that serve a variety of functions, including advertising, promotion, successful marketing, and branding (Keller, 2009). In addition, FGC provides comprehensive and reliable information about the items promoted by a specific company or brand. The term user-generated content (UGC) refers to publicly published media content for non-commercial purposes, which covers any sort of online content created, initiated, distributed, and consumed by users (Lin et al., 2023; Perera et al., 2023). UGC is a type of digital content marketing associated with credibility, trust, and impartial information because it is based on user input and has no commercial benefit, which might reduce the confidence and credibility of the content source (Aljarah et al., 2022). Customer reviews, "like" comments, tweets, and other submissions are examples of user-generated content (UGC) (Dinartanti & Indrawati, 2024). This form of material is critical since it may be consumed or watched by other consumers and is valuable for determining the quality of a brand or company. UGC also provides advantages in product creation, particularly during the idea generation and development phase, because it contains customer information that traditional methodologies cannot access (Ho-Dac, 2020; Timoshenko & Hauser, 2019).

Brand Association

Brand association is the relative strength of a brand's significance to customers (Aaker, 1991) and shows consumers' perception of the brand. Brand association is proposed to include product information in marketing communications (Bilgin, 2018). Brand association is based on brand information retained in customers' minds (Sasmita & Mohd Suki, 2015). Brand association occurs when people are alerted to something linked with the brand. Consumers are more likely to recall and consider a brand with more connotations in their minds. Consumers can form bonds with brands through their exposure to FGC and UGC. The intensity of distribution enables the nodes to be joined. Brands with more interconnections will have higher brand associations (Zhang & Hung, 2020).

H1: FGC positively influences brand association

H2: UGC positively influences brand association

Repurchase Intention

Repurchase intention is defined as a customer's decision to make another purchase from a specific brand after initially experiencing a product (Hong et al., 2019). It also refers to the consumer's intention to buy products from the same company in the future (Shabankareh et al., 2024). A favorable experience and a comfortable atmosphere following the original purchase are the two most

important factors in developing repurchase intention (Sullivan & Kim, 2018). Customer cognitions and emotions that influence the purchase or reuse of a brand or service define repurchase intention. Purchase frequency is the primary determinant of this behavioral indicator of consumer loyalty (Hollebeek et al., 2021). Repurchase intentions have an impact on the future relationship between consumers and organizations, as well as organizational profitability and success (Shabankareh et al., 2022). Consumer trust in a brand can influence consumers in generating repurchase intentions (Dinartanti & Indrawati, 2024).

H3: FGC-influenced brand awareness improves repurchase intention

H4: UGC-influenced brand awareness improves repurchase intention

Structural Model

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The sample method used in this investigation was non-probability sampling combined with purposive sampling and quantitative methodologies. The data collection technique involves the dissemination of online surveys using Google Forms, which are distributed on the Wardah brand user forum. Respondents were invited to complete the questionnaire voluntarily, with no incentives to avoid socially desirable responses. The study was performed in Indonesian and aimed to collect 290 responses from consumers who had purchased and used Wardah brand cosmetics and skin care products, use social media, and live in Jakarta, Bandung, and Surabaya. Secondary data sources for this study include books, journal articles, news, reports, references, and other reliable sources. This study's data analysis technique is structural equation modeling (SEM) utilizing partial least squares (PLS-SEM), and the software utilized to process data is SmartPLS 3.0. After the data is collected, it is then examined using a causal descriptive analysis approach to provide insight into the correlation between variables without drawing broader conclusions.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

According to the survey results, respondents from Surabaya City accounted for 36% (105 respondents), followed by Jakarta City (34% (100 respondents) and Bandung City (29% (85 respondents). Female respondents account for 70% (203 responses). The largest age group was 25-34 years old, with 39% (112 respondents), followed by 18-24 years old at 33% (95 respondents) and 35-44 years old at 14% (42 respondents). In terms of education, 52% (151 respondents) hold a Bachelor's or Diploma degree. In terms of Wardah product use, this study discovered that 26% (76 respondents) have used Uniqlo products for more than three years, 25% (73 respondents) for 3-6 months, and 18% (51 respondents) for more than 1-3 years. This demographic and usage profile provides a complete picture of the respondents' characteristics, shedding light on Wardah's consumer base in Indonesia, particularly Surabaya City, Jakarta, and Bandung, which account for the vast majority of cosmetic consumers in Indonesia.

Table 1. Measurement item of the study

Variables	Items	Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	AVE	Composite Reliability
Firm-generated Content	FGC1	0.868	0.891	0.893	0.752	0.924
	FGC2	0.876				
	FGC3	0.862				
	FGC4	0.864				
	UGC1	0.747	0.795	0.814	0.619	0.866

User-generated content	UGC2	0.751				
	UGC3	0.794				
	UGC4	0.851				
Brand Association	BAS1	0.895	0.896	0.898	0.761	0.927
	BAS2	0.861				
	BAS3	0.871				
	BAS4	0.862				
Repurchase Intention	RI1	0.827	0.705	0.706	0.629	0.836
	RI2	0.777				
	RI3	0.774				

Source: Author’s own creation (2024)

SmartPLS 3.0 was used to analyze data collected from an online distributed questionnaire. Each variable was examined for construct validity, specifically convergent and discriminant validity, and hypotheses were tested. Convergent validity in SEM-PLS is measured by outer loading, with a rule of thumb score of >0.70 indicating good convergent validity (Indrawati, 2015).

In this study, the outer loading of all items for each variable exceeds the 0.70 criterion. The average variance extracted (AVE) values are all more than 0.50, indicating convergent validity. According to Hair et al. (2022), an AVE value greater than 0.50 suggests that the items in a variable have adequate convergent validity.

Furthermore, constructs are deemed very reliable when composite reliability > 0.70, Cronbach's alpha > 0.60, and rho_A > 0.70. In this study, all variables have Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values greater than 0.70, indicating that each indicator for the variable is consistent and reliable. In this study, discriminant validity was tested using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), with a value of 0.90 indicating satisfactory discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2022). Table 2 reveals that the research constructs meet this criterion, indicating the measuring model's discriminant validity.

Table 2. The heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT)

	BAS	FGC	RI	UGC
BAS				
FGC	0.697			
RI	0.501	0.870		
UGC	0.648	0.880	0.778	

Source: Author’s own creation (2024)

DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

This study addresses the first research question, which investigates the impact of SMC dimensions (FGC and UGC) on brand association and how it influences repurchase intention. The contribution of focus necessitates the breakdown of SMC into distinct components that give empirical evidence to demonstrate their relationship with brand association and repurchase intention. The fsquare test is used to determine if predictors of latent variables have a modest, medium, or large effect. Hair et al. (2022) classify fsquare as 0.025 large, 0.01 medium, or 0.005 tiny. Table 3 demonstrates that the research constructs fit these criteria, indicating the effect magnitude or lateral collinearity of each variable in this study.

Table 3. Lateral collinearity

	FGC	UGC	BAS	RI
FGC			0.167	
UGC			0.031	
BAS				0.191
RI				

Source: Author’s own creation (2024)

Furthermore, your investigation yielded various findings, with all hypotheses proving to have a favorable and significant influence. This is because the rule of thumb for the t statistic is a number more than 1.65 (one-tailed) and a p-value less than 0.05 (0.05 error threshold). According to hypothesis 1 in this study, firm-generated content can influence the relative strength of a brand's meaning for customers. Brand association occurs when consumers are offered cues such as product qualities, benefits, or other information associated to the Wardah brand via company-created content. According to hypothesis 2 in this study, user-generated material can influence the relative strength of the Wardah brand's meaning for other consumers.

Brand association will occur when consumers are exposed to cues such as product qualities, benefits, or information relating to the Wardah brand created by other consumers. Consumer-created material is thought to be more trusted by other target consumers (Perera et al., 2023; Poulis et al., 2019; Schivinski et al., 2022; Zia et al., 2022). H3 argues that the relative power of Wardah's brand meaning for consumers after viewing the Wardah company's content leads them to repurchase products. The last hypothesis, H4, indicates that the relative power of Wardah's brand meaning for customers after viewing material made by other consumers motivates them to repurchase.

Table 4. Structural model analysis results

Hypothesis	Relationship	Path Coefficient	t statistic	P-Value	Result
H1	firm-generated content -> brand association	0.474	5.856	0.000	Accepted
H2	user-generated content -> brand association	0.204	2.589	0.005	Accepted
H3	firm-generated content -> brand association -> repurchase intention	0.190	3.742	0.000	Accepted
H4	user-generated content -> brand association -> repurchase intention	0.081	2.405	0.008	Accepted

Source: Author's own creation (2024)

Figure 2. Results of the main effects

The study's concluding finding is that respondents believe that material provided by firms has a greater influence on repurchase intention due to brand awareness than content created by companies. Given the prevalence of fake news, customers should exercise caution when acquiring product information from the Internet and social media (Cheung et al., 2020; Tardin et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

The primary goal of this research is to determine the impact of social media communication on repurchase intention via brand awareness and which component of social media communication is more influential. To achieve this goal, a quantitative method was used, with questionnaires distributed via Google Forms to 290 respondents who met the criteria of having purchased and used Wardah brand cosmetics and skin care products, using social media, and living in Jakarta, Bandung, or Surabaya. The obtained data was then evaluated with SmartPLS 3.0.

This study reveals that social media communication has a positive and significant impact on repurchase intention through brand association. In addition, corporate content has a stronger impact on brand association repurchase intention than consumer-created content. Given the ubiquity of fake news, customers should exercise caution when obtaining product information via the Internet and social media (Cheung et al., 2020; Tardin et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2023).

RECOMMENDATION

In this study, Wardah can improve and innovate in building communication and services through social media, such as providing up-to-date information that is more trustworthy and convinces consumers of Wardah's quality and products, creating positive experiences with consumers, developing loyalty programs, and engaging consumers' emotions with the brand to make consumers more committed to the Wardah brand. Furthermore, Wardah can boost product value and quality, as well as providing the best and most reliable service, so that other consumers have a positive experience with Wardah and leave positive remarks on Wardah's social media accounts.

According to the findings of the analysis, the researcher expects that this study Can be used as a reference for future research, particularly for research that addresses similar concerns and objects. Furthermore, it is believed that this study would bring fresh insights, information, and knowledge in the area of social media marketing for cosmetic companies or other things. The author also proposes that the theories in this study be updated on a regular basis in order to remain fresh and useful in delivering practical and academic solutions. Future study can investigate new theories and factors, such as customer involvement, various dimensions of CBBE, and value co-creation.

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